

Federated learning in food research[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The use of machine learning in food research is sometimes limited due to data sharing obstacles such as data ownership and privacy requirements. Federated learning is a technique to potentially alleviate these obstacles because it allows to train machine learning models locally, keeping the data private and sharing only the learned parameters.

In this review we investigate the use of federated learning in food research. First, we outline a framework that describes the variants of federated learning implementations. Then, we provide an overview of applications of federated learning in food research. Next, we discuss the performance of the models trained with federated learning, and reasons for the use of federated learning. Finally, we categorize the encountered federated learning applications within the federated learning framework. In the discussion, we highlight the knowledge gaps and discuss the potential novel applications.

In this review we examined a total of 86 papers published between 2019 and 2024. The current applications encompass crop disease monitoring, yield prediction, quality assessment, and pesticide residue risk analysis. We observed the general trend of centralized horizontal federated learning, and identified the absence of vertical federated learning, federated transfer learning, and decentralized architectures as research gaps.

1. Introduction

Lack of access to safe and nutritious food is detrimental to the health and wellbeing of people. The sustainable development goals aim to end hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture [1]. One approach to contribute to this goal is to use machine learning models to gain insight in current issues and help to predict future scenarios [2,3].

Machine learning models are algorithms that learn patterns from data to perform a task, such as classifying the content of an image. For instance, a model can be trained to determine whether the fruit in an image is a pear or an apple. The model learns by making adjustments to its parameters based on the data to improve its performance. To ensure adequate and reliable performance, a lot of data is needed to reflect the variety of scenarios, or the model will be biased. When the data originates from just one source, a model might have a limited view of reality. For instance, an apple orchard might have access to many examples of

apples, but just a few examples of pears, making the model better at recognizing apples rather than pears. Thus, data sharing between different data sources is beneficial to the size and variety of datasets, and to the model performance.

Data sharing can be challenging when multiple data owners are involved. This is especially the case with private or sensitive data. Data sharing can be challenging due to legal restrictions and regulations concerning privacy, technical limitations, and data owners being competitors. In the food domain, data owners can be reluctant to share their data due to fear for liability, bad publicity, or loss of business advantage over competitors [4].

Using federated learning, a machine learning model can be trained without disclosing this private or sensitive data [5–7]. In other words, federated learning is a type of privacy-preserving machine learning. Within federated learning the data and the model training are local (i.e., the data does not leave the data's owner storage), and only the model parameters are shared for model improvement [5].

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Machine learning modeling in food research often involves considering data scattered across various research facilities or competing commercial producers reluctant to share their information. Therefore, privacy-preserving machine learning methods, like federated learning, can be very useful for this field. Surprisingly, despite the presence of extensive reviews of federated learning applications have been published in other fields (e.g. agriculture, smart cities, air pollution monitoring, and medicine) ([8–10]; D. C. [11–15]), we have not found a broader review of federated learning in food research. Our work fills this gap by summarizing current achievements, applications, and reasons for the use of federated learning in food research and highlighting encountered pitfalls.

The main research questions we aim to answer in this review are.

- “What food research problems are currently being solved by federated learning?”
- “What are the gaps of federated learning use in food research?”

We structured this paper as follows. In section 2, we define the federated learning framework. Section 3 provides an overview of the current application space of federated learning in food and categorizes all included papers into this framework. In section 4, we give an outlook for future use of federated learning in the food domain.

2. Federated learning framework

The core principle of federated learning is uniquely defined as training the model on locally stored data and only sharing the model parameters. Multiple variants of federated learning exist, and their implementation is detailed by the challenge at hand. In this section we will explain the essential variants of the federated learning framework that we will also use to categorize the papers examined.

Federated learning was introduced as “a decentralized approach of leaving the data distributed on the mobile devices and learning a shared model by locally computed updates” [16]. Following this definition federated learning is applied when each computer (i.e., client node) possesses and does not share their own data. In the federated learning context, each client node trains a machine learning model on their local and private data. Then they share the model parameters, which are aggregated to yield a global model. Such an aggregation step can be performed using different strategies, the simplest of which is averaging [17]. Finally, each local model is updated with the parameters of the new global model. The process of sending the global model to the client nodes, training, and aggregating the results repeats until a maximum number of repetitions or a predefined performance minimum (e.g., model accuracy) is reached. Federated learning has been expanded to a broader range of variants, since its introduction by McMahan et al. [18–24]. We categorize federated learning approaches by type of server architecture, the clients, and data partitioning to form a framework. We divide server architecture into centralized and decentralized [22,24], type of client nodes into cross-device and cross-silo [18,19,24], and data partitioning amongst clients into horizontal federated learning, vertical federated learning, and federated transfer learning [24]. We chose to characterize federated learning using a framework that highlights its collaborative aspect. Our framework focused on the larger questions of who the participants are (type of client), what each participant contributes (data partitioning), and how they communicate (server architecture). Alternative frameworks for categorizing federated learning exist, for instance including privacy mechanism, applicable machine learning model, and methods for solving systems heterogeneity [23]. This type of categorization is focused on the technical details of the implementation.

2.1. Server architecture

The distinction between centralized and decentralized federated

learning (Fig. 1) is determined by the presence of a central server.

In centralized federated learning, a central server is responsible for the aggregation of the results from the client nodes. Such a server is the communication and control center that facilitates the management and regulation of the federated learning process. Letting the server manage the training process presents several advantages. First, a central server releases the client nodes from the burden of both storage and aggregation of the models [22]. Second, the communication between the central server and the client nodes is generally better regulated and protected from eventual malicious attacks [22]. Finally, the presence of only one central server makes the federated learning system easier to operate and manage. Unfortunately, regulating the training process through a single central server has the disadvantage of introducing a single point of failure. In other words, if the central server fails the federated learning process stops, halting the training process because the local results cannot be aggregated.

Decentralized federated learning includes many combinations of client nodes and related connections, and communication protocols such as gossip learning where the client nodes communicate one-on-one with randomly selected peers [25]. In this category of federated learning, there is direct communication between the nodes. This means that the nodes share their learned model parameters among each other to continue learning on the received model or to aggregate the parameters from the received model with their own model. Decentralized federated learning makes the central server obsolete, removing a potential communication bottleneck, a single point of failure, and the need of assuming trustfulness of the central server [22]. In exchange, it increases the computational burden on the client nodes, and requires communication protocols between nodes to be implemented, which introduces new problems. The network topology (i.e., fully connected, partially connected, or node clustering) and the communication protocol (i.e., synchronous or asynchronous) used in a distributed federated learning system can influence the efficiency of the communication, but also robustness, flexibility, security, fault tolerance, and communication cost [26].

2.2. Type of client nodes

The type of client nodes, shown in Fig. 2, can be distinguished in cross-silo and cross-device [19,24]. This distinction has practical implications to the computational resources and the communication bottlenecks.

Cross-silo federated learning usually refers to different organizations such as research institutions or companies that own a large, isolated data source, i.e., a data silo. The number of client nodes and therefore communications are limited, which leads to fewer communication bottlenecks. In cross-silo federated learning, there are usually few carefully selected participants, reducing the risk of a malicious client node trying to disrupt or take unfair advantage of the federated learning system. With this configuration there is also less risk of client nodes being unable to participate due to performance requirements because it is easier to control the quality of the hardware with just few participating client nodes. However, the presence of slow or unresponsive client nodes has a larger influence on model training because a participating node being dropped is more drastic in the cross-silo setting.

Cross-device federated learning can involve millions of mobile or internet of things (IoT) devices. Consequently, there is less oversight on the participating devices, and, in many cases, there will be more variance in the hardware leading to reduced reliability. This type of federated learning faces larger hardware heterogeneity by design but often presents a large quantity and variety of data.

Federated learning can also be applied to edge computing scenarios. Edge computing is the concept of transferring data from data sources, like sensors, IoT devices, or mobile devices, to a geographically proximate edge server (Xia et al., 2021). The edge server is an intermediate step between performing all training on the data-producing devices and

Fig. 1. Server architecture types in federated learning. Figure on the left is a schematic representation of a centralized federated learning architecture. The client nodes communicate their local model updates to the central server that aggregates the results into one model. The aggregated model is communicated back to the client nodes. Figure on the right is an example of a decentralized federated learning architecture, where the client nodes communicate the model updates to each other. The aggregation of the models is performed by the client nodes.

Fig. 2. Types of client nodes in federated learning. Figure on the left displays cross-silo federated learning. In cross-silo federated learning a few organizations, instances, or companies that own large private datasets (data silos) collaborate to train a shared model. Figure on the right represents cross-device federated learning. Cross-device federated learning involves data collected and stored by many (thousands or millions) devices, possibly owned by the same organization.

collecting the data from all the devices at one place. Federated learning in edge computing scenarios can be classified as both cross-device and cross-silo depending on the number of participating edge servers and the amount of data stored at each edge server (Xia et al., 2021). We classified all scenarios employing edge servers as cross-device, because it better reflects the aspect of online data collection from different devices with limited computing resources.

2.3. Data partitioning

Federated learning can also be determined by the way data is partitioned amongst the nodes, as Fig. 3 shows. The distinction in data partitioning is important because it determines how the information is spread across the client nodes. Data partitioning can be distinguished in horizontal federated learning, vertical federated learning, and federated transfer learning [21,23,24].

In horizontal federated learning, each node has different samples with the same, or largely similar features. The aim of horizontal federated learning is to increase the number of training samples with the same set of features. For instance, multiple wheat farmers can collectively train a model to identify wheat diseases from images. The features of the data will not vary, because the wheat and the diseases are expected to look similarly across farms. But because the farmers photograph different wheat plants, the sample space becomes larger. This data partitioning can be applied to both cross-device and cross-silo federated

learning [19].

In vertical federated learning there is a large overlap in samples, but the overlap in features is smaller than in horizontal federated learning. This means that the same individual sample is present across different client nodes with different features. Vertical federated learning is used to increase the feature space of the training data [27]. To illustrate, suppose a shipping company and an apple sauce factory possess information about the same batch of apples. The shipping company owns information about the conditions of the apples during the transport. The apple sauce factory collects information about the quality of apples, together with descriptive measures such as weight. The two companies can employ vertical federated learning to collaboratively train a model for the prediction of the quality of apples. Vertical federated learning typically assumes a different training protocol from horizontal federated learning: all parties need to align the samples in their data, a process called entity alignment [20]. Often the label, in this example the quality of apples, is held by one of the client nodes which acts as a central server. Each client node trains their local part of the model that learns to represent their features. With this federated learning configuration, the intermediate results from the models of each client are incorporated by the central server into a combined model. Then, the central server assesses the combined model by comparing how well the labels match the predictions. Finally, each client node receives client node-specific feedback from the central server (Y. [20]). The participation of all client nodes is necessary for making model predictions, because the

Fig. 3. Data partitioning in federated learning. Horizontal federated learning: each local dataset shares features (weight and color) but contains apples from different farms. Vertical federated learning: The model combines data of the same apple entity that is matched across datasets. Each dataset contains different features. In this example the features are collected at different sites: a farm and a factory. Federated transfer learning: similar to vertical federated learning, however there is less overlap between the samples. Instead of entity matching all the samples used for training, the process often involves learning a shared feature space. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

model needs input from the features spread across the clients.

In federated transfer learning, neither the samples nor the features overlap, or they overlap very slightly [28]. Federated transfer learning aims to improve both the number of samples and the number of features by combining data from different, yet related domains, sources or tasks. Federated transfer learning trains the models in such a way that the mutual information between the tasks is leveraged to help both of them. For example, two companies that collect animal movement sensor data from different breeds of goat and different types of enclosure (free-range rocky terrain vs commercial farm) will own data of different individuals with different behavioral patterns. The free-range goats may display more jumping. The raw data from the commercial goats may be dampened due to the soft terrain. Federated transfer learning enriches the model with more knowledge of different features of goat behavior encountered in different situations. This approach leverages the knowledge acquired from one domain to the other [29]. After the completion of the federated learning training, the model can be fine-tuned to fit the needs of the client better, while still retaining knowledge gathered from the other related domain.

Vertical federated learning and federated transfer learning typically are applied in a cross-silo setting. These partitioning types require additional communication to accommodate entity matching. Moreover, each client node needs to be identifiable, which is not necessarily the case in the cross-device setting [19].

3. Federated learning in food

This section summarizes our findings of federated learning in food. Section 3.1 describes the methods and the search strategy. Section 3.2 summarizes the found literature from different perspectives. Section 3.2.1 provides an overview of federated learning applications in food research. Section 3.2.2 touches upon federated learning model performance in found literature. Section 3.2.3 lists reasons for applying federated learning to food research. Finally, Section 3.3.4 uses the

federated learning framework from Section 2 to summarize the use of federated learning in food research.

3.1. Methods

We selected the literature for this review systematically. We considered a paper as eligible if it contained a use case of federated learning in the food domain. The papers were ideally an implementation of the use case; however, some proposed solutions were also included as long as they were concrete enough. We excluded papers that only contained a brief generic mention like “can be applied to agriculture”, and those that were not written in English.

We obtained the papers through Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and CAB abstracts on the August 15, 2024. We included the exact search queries and their descriptions in the appendix. The search query had two components. The first component included the terms: federated learning, federated approach. The second component included the terms related to food that can be roughly categorized into supply-chain related terms, adulteration related terms, various individual food items, microbial hazards, chemical hazards, and others. We kept the list of included terms as complete as possible.

We limited the search to the title, the abstract, and the keywords. The review focused on “classic” peer-reviewed literature, however encountered “non-classic” literature (i.e., dissertations, conference papers or preprint articles) that met the criteria was also included. Due to the importance of conference proceedings in fast-moving fields such as computer science, we included conference papers on par with journal articles. References to dissertations were explicitly mentioned as such. Additionally, we searched for papers from 2016 onwards, because 2016 was the year of the first publication on federated learning.

In total we collected 548 papers across two rounds. Two researchers checked the papers independently for relevance by reading the titles and abstracts. On top of this, we scanned the references in relevant articles for other relevant literature (snowball approach); however, this did not lead to the discovery of any earlier unseen publications.

3.2. Results

We included 86 distinct papers. The publication dates span between 2019 and 2024. Out of those 86 papers, 9 (10 %) proposed but did not implement federated learning. Fig. 4 shows the reviewing process.

3.2.1. Application overview

Fig. 5 provides a comprehensive overview of federated learning applications across various domains in food research, summarizing the found literature on the topic, highlighting six major categories: food safety hazards, food quality, food production process monitoring and optimization, food fraud, food supply chain, and agriculture-oriented applications. Table 1 shows the detailed list of publications for each category.

3.2.1.1. Food safety hazards

3.2.1.1.1. Chemical hazards. Federated learning applicability in monitoring chemical food safety hazard is critical, as monitoring contaminants such as pesticide residues and heavy metals—known to cause adverse health effects when exceeding safety limits [112]—helps ensure the safety of the food supply.

In case of pesticide residues, the only publicly available data is often only the pass rate - proportion of tested food samples that comply with regulation of certain foods [30]. This restricted data availability makes it challenging to conduct research on bioaccumulation of pesticides because products are only described in a qualitative way: under or above the maximum allowed pesticide residue limit. The sum of smaller quantities that individually are compliant with the residue limit cannot be measured this way. The actual quantitative values related to the

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the paper selection and reviewing process. The reviewers looked at the title and the abstract first to assess the relevance. If the relevance could not be determined on the title and abstract alone, the text body was scanned for more information.

Fig. 5. Bar chart showing the number of papers per federated learning category. The colors represent a grouping of categories (from top to bottom in chart): dark green: Food safety hazards, light green: Food quality, light blue: Food production process monitoring and optimization, light pink: Food fraud light brown: Food supply chain, dark brown: Agriculture oriented applications. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

amount of pesticide residues in food are often scattered across different departments and are not sharable due to data ownership. The only study that makes use of federated learning in this field is that of J. Yu et al. [30] in which the aim is to assess the pesticide residue risk in fruits and vegetables in China. To enable the usage of those data silos, the authors create an entropy risk model that can be computed in parts at each local dataset and combined at the central server. The model gives a more nuanced view on the pesticide residue risks of foods compared to the pass rate based on the qualitative values. This federated learning approach enables more informative predictions of pesticide risk, while keeping the data private.

Heavy metals are another chemical hazard for human health [113]. One federated learning application for detecting heavy metals in soil uses near-infrared spectroscopic data from IoT remote sensing [32]. Horizontal federated learning is applied to an IoT decentralized sensing system to deal with the large scale of sensing by removing the need to collect data from all areas. However, the details of the implementation were not reported in this paper.

A perspective paper [31] proposes detecting and predicting heavy metal contamination of soil and water using federated learning using an edge cloud server. Federated learning is presented as a potential way of facilitating the use of various data types, satellite imagery in combination of in-situ sampling data, gathered at the edges of the edge cloud server while keeping the sources private.

3.2.1.1.2. Biological hazards. Qian et al. [4] reviewed potential federated learning applications in biological food safety domains, particularly those involving pathogen contamination. Their review paper proposes a wide range of potential food safety application domains for federated learning and other private data sharing methods. The authors identify key food safety data types with varying privacy concerns, and propose, amongst others, federated learning as a solution to enhance models by privately sharing data across organizations. For example, graphic information system models that combine microbial data and environmental data, which are costly to gather, can benefit from federated learning to improve spatial and temporal data distribution without exposing sensitive information [4]. Quantitative microbial risk assessment models for, among others, the prediction of foodborne illness or recall likelihoods can reduce uncertainty and improve validation by securely integrating data from multiple sources [4]. Agent-based models for pathogen prediction and public health models for foodborne disease outbreaks can benefit from federated learning by data sharing to improve the parameter estimates and to improve data varieties [4].

3.2.1.2. Food quality. Federated learning has been applied in water quality assessment and monitoring, described in the papers by Park et al. [33], Vellingiri et al. [34], and Zhu [35]. Clean water is not only essential for consumption, but it is also needed for agriculture. If contaminated, irrigation water can lead to food hazards in crops [114]. That is why essential water sources, such as natural water bodies or water from treatment companies, ought to be frequently monitored. The traditional type of water quality monitoring requires more hands-on personnel [115]. Furthermore, some water bodies are difficult or dangerous for personnel to reach due to factors such as remote locations. [35]. These factors make using federated learning to automate the process beneficial.

Park et al. [33] tackle the problem of monitoring and prediction of green tide; an overgrowth of algae in water. The data was gathered on the nation-wide scale in South Korea using smart IoT sensors, edge servers, and a central cloud. The IoT sensors enable monitoring of various green tide indicators such as temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen. The data cannot feasibly be sent to a central server in real-time, due to the large geographic spread of the sensor locations and the limited range of the sensor signals. Furthermore, it is not efficient to have a single access point for data collection. This is why multiple local

Table 1

Federated learning applications in food research. “**” indicates articles that proposed the use of federated learning for a certain goal without conducting experiments.

Application	Subapplication	Authors (year)	Modality	Data type	Data Partition	
Food safety hazards	Chemical	[30]	Tabular/time series	Pesticide detection	Horizontal	
		[31]*	Imaging, Tabular	Several types of (unspecified) data		
Food quality	Biological	[32]	Imaging	NIR spectra of soil samples	Horizontal	
		[4]*	Various	Various		
	Food quality	Food quality	[33]	Tabular/time series	Sensor data	Horizontal
			[34]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal
			[35]	Imaging	Camera monitoring	Horizontal
			[36]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal
			[37]	Tabular	Sensor data, spectral data	Horizontal
			[38]	Imaging	Ultraviolet visible and near infrared spectrograms	Horizontal
Food production process monitoring and optimization	Animal monitoring	[39]*	Imaging	Spectral images		
		[40]	Imaging	Chicken images	Horizontal	
		[41]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal	
		[42]*	Tabular	Milk content, behavior, genome data		
		[43]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal	
		[44]	Imaging	Spectrogram (visual representation of sound recordings)	Horizontal	
	Process monitoring and optimization	Process monitoring and optimization	[45]	Time series	Ultrasonic sensor	Transfer learning
			[46]	Tabular	Irrigation demand, evapotranspiration, infiltration from cropland	Horizontal
			[47]	Time series	Water consumption	Unspecified
			[48]	Imaging	Water foam images	Horizontal
			[49]	Tabular	World states and actions	Horizontal
			[50]*	Tabular	Sensor data	
			[51]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal
			[52]*	Tabular	Sensor data	
			[14]	Tabular	New York Water consumption from Kaggle	Horizontal
			[53]	Imaging	Images of weeds	Horizontal
			[54]	Tabular	NIR imaging	Horizontal
			[55]	Tabular	Sensors	Horizontal
[56]	Tabular	Sensors	Horizontal			
[57]	Time series	Sensors	Horizontal			
[58]	Time series	Weather, water level	Horizontal			
Food fraud	Food fraud	[59]	Tabular	Fraud type, product category, year, origin country, control country	Horizontal	
Food supply chain	Food supply chain	[60]	Tabular	Sampling data of daily food supervision and management from the National Market Supervision Administration	Horizontal/Vertical	
	Security of food systems	Security of food systems	[61]	Time series	Network traffic, sensor, actuator	Horizontal
			[62]	Time series	Sensor data	Horizontal
			[63]	Time series	Traffic data	Horizontal
			[64]	Tabular	Approved number of blocks, online time, net stake investment	Horizontal
			[65]	Imaging	Food images	Horizontal
			[66]	Tabular	Network traffic data, sensor data	Horizontal
			[67]	Sensor	Temperature, ripeness	Horizontal
			[68]	Time series	Traffic data	Horizontal
			[69]	Sensor	Soil, temperature, nutrients	Transfer learning
Agriculture oriented applications	Consumer side	[70]	Tabular	Beer preferences	Horizontal	
	Digitalization	[71]	Tabular	Survey, genome	Horizontal	
		[72]*		Sensor data		
	Crop disease	Crop disease	[73]*	Imaging, Sensor	Fruit images and E-Nose data	
			[74]*	Imaging, Sensor	Rice images	
			[75]	Imaging	Strawberry images	Horizontal
			[76]	Imaging	Strawberry images	Horizontal
			[77]	Imaging	Strawberry images	Horizontal
			[78]	Imaging	Banana leaf images	Horizontal
			[79]	Imaging	Banana leaf images	Horizontal
[80]			Imaging	Banana leaf images	Horizontal	
[81]			Imaging	Banana leaf images	Horizontal	
[82]			Imaging	Guava images	Horizontal	
[83]			Imaging	Jute images	Horizontal	
[84]			Imaging	Sunflower images	Horizontal	
[85]			Imaging	Parsley images	Horizontal	
[86]			Imaging	Coffee images	Horizontal	
[87]			Imaging	Wheat images	Horizontal	
[88]			Imaging	Maize images	Horizontal	
[89]			Imaging	UAV-gathered images	Horizontal/Vertical	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Application	Subapplication	Authors (year)	Modality	Data type	Data Partition
		[90]	Imaging	Orchard and apple images	Horizontal
		[91]	Imaging	Fruit images	Horizontal
		[92]	Imaging	Hyperspectral tomato images	Horizontal
		[93]	Imaging	UAV-gathered images	Horizontal
		[94]	Imaging	Rice leaf images	Horizontal
		[95]	Imaging	Orange images	Horizontal
		[96]	Imaging	Plant images	Horizontal
		[97]	Tabular, Imaging, Sensor	Air and soil humidity and temperature data, soil NPK and EC, and camera HSVs	Horizontal
		[98]	Imaging	PlantVillage dataset (images from different crops)	Horizontal
		[99]	Imaging	Wheat images	Horizontal
		[58]	Imaging	PlantVillage dataset (images from different crops)	Horizontal
		[100]	Imaging	Rice leaf images	Horizontal
		[101]	Imaging	Wheat images	Horizontal
	Yield prediction	[102]	Tabular	Weather and soil sensor data	Horizontal
			Imaging	Satellite images	Horizontal
		[103]	Tabular	Sensor data	Horizontal
		[104]	Tabular	Breeding test phenotypes, environmental meteorology	Vertical
		[105]	Tabular	Weather, soil, environment sensors	Horizontal
		[106]	Tabular	Climatic data	Horizontal
		[107]	Tabular	Weather and soil sensor data	Horizontal
		[108]	Imaging	UAV-gathered images	Horizontal
	Food image classification	[109]	Imaging	Food images	Transfer learning
		[110]	Imaging	Fruit images	Horizontal
		[111]	Imaging	Near-infrared hyperspectral pasture images	Horizontal

edge servers are used to collect the sensor data. Horizontal federated learning was applied to use the sensor data on the edge servers to train models locally and aggregate the parameters into a global model.

Another water quality application focuses on predicting pollution of the Cauvery River in India [34]. The choice for applying federated learning is motivated from the data privacy perspective and focuses more on enabling collaboration between different parties, in this case water monitoring sites. This data is similar to the data from Park et al. [33], with the difference of the data being collected at monitoring site-level, making it a cross-silo problem.

Kathen et al. [36] use a fleet of autonomous surface vehicles for water quality monitoring by scouting water bodies and looking for pollution peaks. They use centralized federated learning with edge server structure in the second stage of their research, where they gather more detailed data and train specialized models for each zone of the water body. After this, the models from different zones are used to update the centrally learned initial model.

The final water quality example by Zhu [35], employs sensors, in this case cameras, edge servers, and centralized horizontal federated learning setting. The author uses a convolutional neural network, which is a computer vision model, to assess the quality of the water based on chromatic information in image data.

Federated learning is also applied to milk quality assessment in liquid [37] and powder [38] form. The milk quality is dependent on its contents and can be analyzed using light spectra from various ranges of light. Vimalajeewa et al. [37] use Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy samples for liquid milk quality assessment. This work compares the state-of-the-art techniques for analyzing Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy data to their own composite model in both federated and non-federated settings. Gulati et al. [38] use ultraviolet illumination visible spectral images collected for both pure and ad-hoc adulterated skimmed milk powder. The authors use this case study as a proof-of-concept for combining blockchain technology and federated learning in supply chains to achieve a federated learning workflow that ensures protection against malicious attacks on performance from both the server and the clients. Such a federated learning architecture transfers some of the functionality of a centralized server to a distributed ledger that can choose which local models to aggregate and when to aggregate them based on predefined criteria.

Finally, the perspective review by Müller-Maatsch et al. [39]

suggests the usage of federated learning for improving the usability of portable miniature spectral devices for measuring safety, authenticity, and quality of various food commodities. The challenge they address is the large bottleneck caused by the need to calibrate and re-calibrate such instruments; a task for which the necessary databases are often device specific, food specific, or contamination specific. Due to such heterogeneity across these datasets, eventual similarities between databases are not being leveraged to their full potential. In consequence, every change is met with a lot of repetitive work. A federated learning network is proposed to link a data sample to different data sources such as reference methods database and spectral imaging database.

3.2.1.3. Food production process monitoring and optimization. Federated learning supports diverse applications in food production process monitoring and optimization, including animal monitoring (e.g., day-age classification, health, and welfare), assessing dairy cattle genetic potential, and monitoring beer fermentation among other related tasks. Machine learning models have been widely used in this domain. However, developing accurate machine learning models requires large and diverse datasets that a single company may not possess. Collaboration can contribute to better models, but sharing data with competitors raises privacy and competitive concerns. Federated learning addresses this issue by combining data sources securely, enhancing product quality, efficiency, and innovation while maintaining competitive boundaries and data privacy.

3.2.1.3.1. Animal monitoring. The first application we encountered was chicken day-age classification by Y. Huang et al. [40]. Knowing the exact age of a chicken helps to assess the health of the animal, to choose the optimal breeding cycle, feeding cycle, and slaughter time of respectively chickens to reduce costs and environmental pollution. The model takes chicken images and trains them in a federated manner on horizontally partitioned local data. Each local model is individualized through filter pruning, and federated learning is applied as a form of distributed learning.

Another aspect to monitor is the animal health and welfare that can be assessed through observing the animal's behavior. Animal activity recognition traditionally relies on time-consuming and labor-intensive visual and behavioral observation [116]. Nowadays, it can also be automated using wearable motion data sensors on the animals, as shown

from Mao et al. [41] and Arshad et al. [43]. The raw data can be interpreted with models trained to classify the behaviors into categories like eating, sleeping, walking etcetera. Mao et al. [41] highlight that, although federated learning has the potential of enlarging the size of available data, animal behavior patterns can vary within individuals and between farms leading to client drift, where each client starts to deviate from one another during local training. Furthermore, gradient conflicts might occur during aggregation. Consequently, this work proposes solutions to both problems to enhance convergence towards a global model applicable to all individual animals. We can find another application of federated learning relatable to animal behavior in the work of Borgianni et al. [44], where the authors built a federated learning model to predict the presence of honeybees in hives based on the sound that can be recorded on-site.

Gengler [42] proposes utilizing sensor data, usually meant for management applications, to assess and improve the genetic potential of dairy cattle. One of the challenges listed was the governance and ownership of the sensor data. The author hypothesizes that federated learning will create opportunities for new animal evaluation methods, for instance through training on continuously updated data. The training based on the raw sensor data can result in phenotypic sensor algorithms or even federated genomic prediction models that could enhance breeding research.

3.2.1.3.2. Process monitoring and optimization. Next application addresses the challenges of the monitoring of fermentation processes of beer using ultrasonic sensors and temperature. Due to the length of the fermentation process, it is difficult to collect enough data to train models for each vessel separately, especially for small and medium enterprises. The ultrasonic waves can vary each time a sensor is attached, even if the same procedure is followed and the sensor type and vessel materials stay the same [117]. Each fermentation vessel produces different patterns that are not directly transferable. Bowler et al. [45] test domain adaptation strategies to combine data obtained from a laboratory (source domain) and industrial data (target domain). Federated transfer learning is used as a privacy-friendly version of domain adaptation. Federated transfer learning is compared against combining the data and fine-tuning the models on the target domain. Akbari et al. [49] use synchronous centralized federated learning for optimizing the paths of UAV based edge devices in a way that it minimizes the age of information and the network energy usage of real time monitoring for smart farming. Another example of federated learning in smart farming can be found in Siniosoglou et al. [57], where they used a centralized, horizontal strategy to build a neural network model to predict future field conditions from historical data.

Federated learning for process monitoring is also present in water-related research. Cui et al. [46] suggest federated learning as a future extension of their groundwater level modelling research. Federated learning is proposed for a groundwater level IoT system composed of sensors, edge servers and a central cloud server to obtain up-to-date data. Elhachmi and Kobbane [47] use a similar approach to build a federated learning linear regression model on simulated water data to predict water consumption. The research conducted by Singh et al [55] and Singh et al [56] focuses on the implementation of edge computing for the development of federated learning system for water management and irrigation, respectively. Another example of federated learning based on edge computing can be found in Thonglek and Maipradit [58]. In this study, the authors build a federated learning model to predict the water level using historical data on water and weather. Bera et al. [51] implement edge computing to reduce energy requirements and connectivity challenges related to a federated learning system for irrigation monitoring. Mato et al. [48] use models for texture segmentation to measure the amount of foam in wastewater to optimize the best moment for its removal. Horizontal, centralized cross-silo federated learning is applied on two tanks within one wastewater treatment plant to test the possibilities for extending the model to multiple wastewater treatment plants. Finally, Pei et al. [50] suggest combining federated learning with

“Internet of Underwater Things” for applications such as water quality monitoring, underwater life detection, flood forecasting, underwater detection, and marine energy transfer.

3.2.1.4. Food fraud. Federated learning is applied to the food safety research on predicting food fraud based on historical data. In their paper, Gavai et al. [59] simulate a scenario where known food fraud cases for different geographic locations are confidential and not shared beyond their borders. Such experimental setting allowed to combine the food fraud data from the European Union Rapid Alert for Food and Feed¹ database and the United States Economically Motivated Adulteration² database. The data was divided among three clients. One client got the data from the United States database only, and the other two got the data from the European Union split by “before and after 2014”, leading to a realistic data split scenario where data is distributed in a heterogeneous way. The authors train Bayesian Network models on local data, combined data, and the local data in federated learning setting to compare the federated and non-federated scenarios.

3.2.1.5. Food supply chain. This section describes the uses of federated learning across food supply chains. Food supply chains often include multiple stages from production to consumption. Data sharing across the different stages is not always possible or optimal. Data sharing may create delays [67], or privacy or security vulnerabilities. Moreover, trust is an essential aspect of supply chains [118,60]. This area lends itself to federated learning as recognized by T.H. Liu et al. [119]. Within food research, X. Zhang et al [60] look specifically into collaboration across food supply chains through the use of vertical and horizontal federated learning, paired with blockchain technology. They test their architecture in an artificial experimental setup using a cowpea safety dataset.

3.2.1.5.1. Security of food systems. Federated learning can be applied to ensure the security of the food systems. Food systems increasingly rely on IoT technology, exposing them to cybersecurity threats. For instance, an attack targeting a water pump caused a failure of a water treatment plant in Illinois in 2011 [120]. Federated learning fits well with the use of machine learning to enhance security against cyber-attacks in industrial IoT settings [61] by allowing data to remain localized. This privacy-preserving training approach addresses the stakeholder’s reluctance to share sensitive and private data. Using a real-world Secure Water Treatment dataset, Jahromi et al. [61] train a model to effectively detect previously unseen attacks in a horizontal federated scenario, combining data from different sources. A similar federated learning application is introduced by Bahadoripour et al. [66] where centralized horizontal federated learning is used for training a cyber-attack detection model for industrial control systems. The authors apply domain adaptation as a preprocessing step to map the data from each client into a shared feature space before applying federated learning, transforming it from a federated transfer learning problem to a horizontal federated learning problem. Finally, Zeng et al. [68] has introduced an adversarial sample generation method and a training method to enhance adversarial robustness of federated learning systems in the secure water treatment domain.

In the face of IoT sensors being more frequently employed on farms, it is important to take the safety of food systems into consideration to prevent vulnerabilities to hacker attacks [121]. The work of P. Kumar et al. [62], Friha et al. [63], and Praharaaj et al. [69] focus on this use case of the protection of agricultural IoT using federated learning intrusion models. Alrashdi et al. [65] integrate contrastive learning to enhance the model’s ability to distinguish between clean and adversarial examples of food images, thereby improving robustness of federated learning in

¹ Rapid Alert for Food and Feed Window: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>.

² Economically Motivated Adulteration: <https://www.fda.gov/food/compliance-enforcement-food/economically-motivated-adulteration-food-fraud>.

internet of visual things systems.

As federated learning may not ensure full security, additional improvements have been proposed. Bala and Kaur [64] highlight the use of federated learning and blockchain in the light of crop insurance. Crop insurance requires companies to gather personal data from the farmers. Blockchain as a storage solution is stated to offer transparency and real-time traceability, but at the same time requires a solid consensus strategy to be secure and prevent malicious actors from infiltrating the system. The authors suggest a solution using federated learning to train a model for calculating trust scores that can be used for a reliable Proof-Of-Stake mechanism for blockchain.

3.2.1.5.2. Consumer side of the food supply chain. From the consumer perspective of the food supply chain, recent research has also explored how federated learning can support modelling individual preferences, which can streamline the customization of product offerings. Z. Liu et al. [70] apply federated learning to consumer preference of beer brands. In this scenario, each simulated consumer finds different aspects of beer important. Federated learning is implemented to keep the consumers' preferences private by only sharing their reward based on the choices made during training, without disclosing which aspects they find important. When the consumers' preferences are modelled using the collective regret obtained through federated learning, the simulated optimal beer choice is reached faster and with less collective accumulated regret. Next, in a more recent work, Sudharson et al. [71] propose a system that utilizes user preferences collected via a survey, health goals, microbiome data, and wearable device readings to recommend informed dietary choices.

3.2.1.6. Agriculture oriented applications. Agriculture-oriented applications of federated learning indirectly influence multiple aspects of the food system such as food safety, nutrient availability, and product quality. Better yield prediction and tailored crop selection reduce pesticide reliance, preserve food safety, and promote a stable, healthful food supply.

3.2.1.6.1. Federated learning in a broader scope of agriculture digitalization. Federated learning can be viewed from the broader perspective of the digitalization of the agriculture. A literature review by Abbasi et al. [122] captures and analyses various developments in smart farming. The digital technologies that were included in the description were the IoT technology, wireless sensor networks, cloud and edge computing, autonomous robotics systems, big data and analytics, machine learning, deep learning, decision support systems, cyber-physical systems, and digital twins. Federated learning was named as a solution to "digital transformation's cyber-security and data privacy challenges". Salem et al. [72] introduced a future vision for smart farming in United Arab Emirates that incorporated federated learning with edge server technology to timely detect adverse conditions and automatically react to the signals to optimize farming through digitalization.

3.2.1.6.2. Crop disease. Crop disease identification and severity estimation is a prevalent use case in the food research. Here, federated learning can be useful to tackle challenges related to data sharing such as privacy concerns and communication cost. Many papers focus on image data for various fruits and vegetables, such as rice ([74,94]; Tripahty et al., 2024), strawberries([75]; N. [76]; S. [77]), bananas (A. [78]; S. [79]; S. [80]; V. [81]), guava (D. [82]), jute (K. [83]), sunflower (J. [84]), parsley [85], coffee (V. [86]), wheat [87,99], maize [88], and soybean [89]. Two papers are about disease identification in orchards [90,91]. Mamba Kabala et al. [98] use the PlantVillage dataset for an extensive exploration of federated learning for disease identification on four types of crops. They investigate the effect of using different values for number of clients, communication rounds, and iterations, as well as different neural network architectures for their federated learning setup. Finally, one paper implements a system for multiple agricultural pest identification independent of the plant species cultivated [93]. All of the papers focus on imaging data of healthy and diseased plants.

Khan et al. [93], Konyar and Gahrooei [92] and C. Yu et al. [89] focus on images obtained through unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) devices. C. Yu et al. [89] and Konyar and Gahrooei [92] consider data obtained by UAV devices and collected at the edge servers. Khan et al. [93] mentioned UAV technology as the goal, however the experiments are performed on a public dataset without simulating the UAV scenario. Mehta, Kukreja, and Gupta [88] mention the problem of specificity and the capabilities of identifying diseases on the individual plant-level being low when remote sensing like drones or satellite images are being utilized. Their solution focuses on the individual-level images of diseased plants. The remaining papers on this topic use openly accessible datasets [88] enriched with images from growers and experts [87].

3.2.1.6.3. Yield prediction. Federated learning enables secure, collaborative yield prediction model training across diverse agricultural conditions to guide preventive measures, optimize crop variety selection, and facilitate private data utilization in both cross-silo and cross-device settings.

Three publications include yield prediction of soybean crops [102, 103] and maize crop varieties [104]. Durrant et al. [102] use the soybean prediction problem as a use case to demonstrate horizontal federated learning and its potential for data sharing in agriculture. The task is to predict the average observed yield per unit area within American counties that pose as data silos. They use sequences of remote satellite images taken before harvest, and tabular data of the weather and soil as two different data-driven scenarios. Manoj et al. [103] focus on the same task of federated soybean yield prediction and also applied centralized, horizontal federated learning in a cross-silo setting. Their motivation was to contribute to the agricultural production risk management demands by overcoming data sharing obstacles. A. Li et al. [107] use the same task to test a model pruning algorithm that respects different local distributions and increases communication efficiency with the same federated learning settings. Q. Zhang et al. [104] use vertical, cross-silo federated learning for the selection of the maize variety based on the optimal yield prediction for collaborative plant breeding. The authors use data collected from 248 trial sites that posed as client nodes. They consider varieties of maize to be the overlapping samples and phenotypic traits and environmental conditions to be features that could differ across client nodes. The authors apply a federated random forest model that requires some central knowledge of the features and samples. The central server receives encoded and encrypted aligned feature codes to perform decision-tree-type training.

We identified two publications on the selection of the correct crop from a wider range of plant species based on the weather and soil conditions [105,106]. Bera et al. [105] considers ten plant species to create a crop prediction model that can be used in an app for crop recommendation called CropReco. Bera et al. [105] use federated learning to enable model training on the edge servers that gathered data directly from the sensors, which we consider to be a cross-device setting. Idoje et al. [106] investigate federated learning Gaussian Naïve Bayes models that can predict the optimal choice between rice, maize or chickpea crops based on climatic features in a horizontally partitioned dataset.

3.2.1.6.4. Food image classification. Federated learning approaches have also been explored for more specialized tasks in image classification. Ooi et al [54] show examples of federated learning aiming to improve the identification of weed plants to optimize pesticide spraying. Herbicide used on crops can be harmful to both people working in the fields and ingesting the products. V. Huang et al. [111] perform experiments to test client drop out resilience of federated learning models in the context of weed detection. The other two papers in this category [109,110] are likewise not written from the perspective of solving agricultural problems. Instead, they focus on advancing the field of federated learning with food image classification as an example use case.

3.2.2. Federated learning performance in the food research

Some included papers only propose future directions of federated learning; therefore, they do not include performance results [4,31,39,

[123]. For the papers that implement and test a federated learning system, the question remains how well the research setup matches the problems of federated learning applied to data collected by different organizations or devices. One of the challenges of federated learning is non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) data [124] that includes quality skew, quantity skew, feature skew, and label skew ([124]; Saeed et al., 2025). The data across clients real-life scenarios is not guaranteed to have the same distribution, for instance due to differences amongst farms. Some farms collect more data than others (quantity skew), data of lower quality (quality skew). The label distribution and feature distribution can be different across farms due to factors such as environmental conditions or the way a farm is managed. Non-IID can lead to model bias and unfairness between clients (Saeed et al., 2025). The lack of guarantees for data homogeneity can introduce problems with model convergence and performance [125]. However, the problem of non-IID data is not addressed when the data is artificially partitioned into equal, balanced sets. Many of the authors are not explicit in their specification of the data division method [34,35,37,61], or partition the data in an optimistic, uniformly distributed way [38, 91]). The results from experiments on homogeneously distributed data probably do not reflect real-life scenarios. Below we summarize some of the federated learning model results.

Jahromi et al. [61] conclude that a federated learning anomaly detection outperforms non-federated learning methods with only partial access to the data, solves privacy and security issues bound to sharing data directly and circumvents the time-consuming training problem on a single centralized server by performing the training in a decentralized way. However, their results did not consider the non-IID data problem, and the models were not compared to a model trained on the combined data. The latter is useful to assess how well federated learning performs against the optimal case where all data is shared directly. Vellingiri et al. [34] achieve an accurate performance and reduced training time using the federated learning approach compared to the individually trained local models. The work of Vimalajeewa et al. [37] achieve a performance similar to that of the state-of-the-art convolutional neural network model for milk classification under the federated learning setting. Zhu [35] reports that the federated learning models reached the same performance as a convolutional neural network faster, while also reducing the human and material resource requirements. Gulati et al. [38] compare their Blockchain-Event Triggered Asynchronous federated learning scheme with another synchronous federated learning system, and synchronous federated learning on the Blockchain. Their federated learning communication scheme achieves similar performance but with more claims to protection against malicious agents. Similarly, Park et al. [33] compares different scheduling scenarios within the federated learning framework. The authors conclude that their scheduling method achieves effective performance due to balanced data gathering. However, real-world factors like positions of the network components, distribution ratios and communication channel qualities are not considered in the current simulation.

Some papers reflect the non-IID data problem by dividing the data amongst the artificial clients in a realistic manner. The data is divided based on the geographical location [30,59,102] or time [59]. The two experiments performed by Gavai et al. [59] show that federated learning setting does not substantially decrease the performance when compared to a model trained on combined data. The difference between locally trained models and federated learning is not straightforward, because in some cases the local performance decreases. The authors conclude that it is most likely due to data heterogeneity.

Y. Huang et al. [40] perform a detailed analysis testing many scenarios, including a varying number of clients, different data divisions across clients, lightweight model versus original model comparison, and federated learning or no federated learning comparison. The accuracy of models using federated learning is consistently better and the difference in performance between the lightweight version and the original version of the models seems to be smaller in the federated setting. The different

computer vision models tested seem to have a varying degree of robustness against various data divisions settings.

To get a better view of the effects of federated learning on e.g. performance results of food research applications, we added a qualitative analysis (Table 2). The qualitative analysis contrasts examples of experiments and results presented in the literature. This cross-study overview demonstrates that there was variation in the conducted experiments, despite the usual focus on final model performance. Sometimes federated learning was treated as a fixed factor and the only thing being varied was model architecture. Other times, specific aspects of the federated learning were varied, such as the averaging algorithm, the division of data between the clients (size and label distribution), or the federated updates being synchronized or parallel.

3.2.3. Reasons for federated learning

The main reasons listed by the included literature to use federated learning can be categorized into using federated learning to train models on local data that otherwise would not be shared and using federated learning as a form of efficient resource allocation. In this context, we define resource limitations to be any limitations concerning computing power, storage place, or communication (e.g., latency or overload) that limit the capability of collecting the data centrally. Efficient resource allocation aims to counter these problems.

The first argument encompasses the interconnected concepts of data sharing [4,30,31,38,39,59], retaining privacy ([38,39,59]; C. [4,31,34, 37]), data access rights and confidentiality [30,39,59], security [59], and data ownership [37,59]. Some combination of these terms is provided as a reason in many of the encountered papers ([42,47,63,93,102, 106]; P. [41,50,62,87,88,91,103,104]). This line of reasoning naturally fits the cross-silo setting where multiple data owners want to collaborate without sharing their data.

The argument of resource allocation is often encountered in edge computing scenarios [40,42,49,47,50,63,70,89–91,93,106]. For instance, federated learning is useful in cases where the data is geographically scattered and resides on devices with a weak signal range. This might be the case with IoT technology where federated learning is posed as a solution to train the models in a feasible and robust manner on the edge servers that collect the data from nearby devices. For example, Park et al. [33] find federated learning to be a robust solution in a setting with online data gathering, where communicating the data to a central server is not feasible. Other problems concerning resources include centralized IoT communication, resource management, limitation to transmission distances, burdens of massive accesses, limitations of ICT infrastructure, and limitations on personnel [33,35,37].

Some papers have the advancement of the federated learning technology as their main goal and use food-related data to benchmark their research. For example, Polap and Wozniak [110] and Hsieh et al. [109] focus on federated learning aggregation. Polap and Wozniak [110] used the fruit image classification problem to showcase an image augmentation technique and a new federated learning aggregation scheme. Hsieh et al. [109] introduced a voting scheme that aims to replace regular federated learning aggregation, such as averaging the model parameters, for food image classification. Alrashdi et al. [65] investigated the robustness of federated learning against adversarial attacks in IoT systems. As a final example, V. Huang et al. [111] study the fault tolerance of federated learning against unreliable clients that may drop out during training or have inconsistent configuration of the model.

3.2.4. Federated learning framework perspective on the food research

Fig. 6 summarizes how the current and proposed applications within food related research span the federated learning landscape.

Most papers found on this topic either use a centralized architecture or do not specify the architecture. The classic centralized architecture involves one central aggregation server that the client nodes send parameter updates to. One special case of centralized federated learning architecture uses a hierarchical server structure with multiple

Table 2

Cross-study overview of the conducted experiments and achieved results. This overview demonstrates that there was variation in the conducted experiments, despite the usual focus on final model performance. FL vs subset = Federated learning vs trained on data subset (e.g., single client). FL vs centralized = Federated learning vs trained on the whole dataset (centralized training). Different architectures = Federated learning with different model architectures. Differential privacy = Federated learning with differential privacy. Synchronous vs asynchronous = Federated learning with synchronous vs asynchronous updates. Varied clients = Federated learning with a varied number of clients and/or amount of data per client. Label skew = Federated learning with varied label skew between clients. Multiple aggregation = Federated learning with different aggregation algorithms.

Reference	Domain	Modality	FL vs subset	FL vs centralized	Different architectures	Differential privacy	Synchronous vs asynchronous	Varied clients	Label skew	Multiple aggregation	Metrics	Additional comments on selected results
[61]	Security of food systems	Tabular	yes		yes						Accuracy, precision, recall, F-score	The federated learning setup increases accuracy with 6.76 % vs traditional non-federated learning setup on local data. The approximate peaks of the results distributions were 0.45 for locally trained models and 0.67 for the federated learning models. This corresponds to a 39.29 % difference.
[34]	Food quality	Tabular	yes		yes					Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score. Computation time per step (training time on client-side)		
[37]	Food quality	Tabular		yes	yes		yes			yes	Residual Sum of Square (RSS), coefficient of determination (R^2)	
[38]	Food quality	Imaging					yes				Accuracy, computation time per step	
[40]	Animal monitoring	Imaging		yes	yes			yes	yes		Accuracy, recall, precision, communication overhead (original x pruned)	
[33]	Food quality	Tabular						yes			Accuracy, number of edges satisfying the minimum data size D (cumulative over all FL iterations)	For lower data requirements and baseline random assignment, all edge servers were engaged in each training iterations, but only 66.4 %–68.8 % of those training iterations reached an accuracy of 80 % or higher. Setting the minimal data requirements parameter to a higher value of 50 or 100 meant that not all edge servers were engaged in training at each iteration, but the trained local models achieved an accuracy of 80 % or more in 90.5 % up to 100 % cases. These results showed that setting requirements on the local data size before training has an influence on the performance of the local models and on their training frequency.
[91]	Crop disease	Imaging			yes						Accuracy, mean average precision (MAP), detection time	This work did not compare the FL performance to other scenario's. The paper included a comparison between 4 model architectures within federated learning setting.
[102]	Yield prediction	Tabular, Imaging	yes	yes	yes	yes				yes	Root mean square error (RMSE)	Federated learning improved on the local training baseline by approximately 22.75 % (image data) and 39.81 % (tabular data). Federated learning also performed almost as good as centralized training, with a disparity in RMSE of 6.68 %. The addition of differential privacy (DP) worsens the RMSE score by approximately 15.19 % (image) and 19.76 % (tabular). FL with DP still performed better than the

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Reference	Domain	Modality	FL vs subset	FL vs centralized	Different architectures	Differential privacy	Synchronous vs asynchronous	Varied clients	Label skew	Multiple aggregation	Metrics	Additional comments on selected results
[59]	Food Fraud	Tabular	yes	yes							Area under the ROC curve (AUC), average sensitivity, average specificity	local baseline, but worse than FL without DP. The AUC score difference between the centralized and federated learning training was 4.54 % in favor of federated learning. The difference between local performance was 7.56 % in favor of the local model for one client. The other two benefited from the global federated learning with 3.08 % and 2.73 % AUC score difference.
[30]	Food safety hazards-chemical	Tabular/ time series			yes						Qualitative analysis of the risk assessment method (risk entropy obtained through FL) with	

aggregation servers (Deveraj et al., 2024).

There are a few exceptions using a decentralized architecture [67,95,108,126]. For instance, Carrascosa et al. [95] use a decentralized federated learning scheme where the agents aggregate models from their neighbors. Nie et al. [108] develop a decentralized federated learning model for yield prediction in jujube fields using blockchain technology for secure communication between nodes. Gulati et al. [38] combine centralized federated learning architecture with a blockchain scheme that made the setting more decentralized.

Most applications and propositions focus on horizontal partitioning. Q. Zhang et al. [104] include application explicitly focusing on the vertical federated learning where the client nodes did not have access to the same set of features. Vertical and horizontal federated learning can also be combined. C. Yu et al. [89] use a hybrid learning scheme, where vertical federated learning is applied at edge server level and horizontal federated learning is applied at central server level. X. Zhang et al. [60] use the opposite structure where the models are first trained in a cross-device horizontal manner, grouped by the type of client (production, enterprise). This is followed by a cross-silo vertical learning scheme on a higher level. Some applications include transfer learning elements, such as the work of Hsieh et al. [109]. In their work, Hsieh et al. pretrain the model on a source task and fine-tune it on the target task. Praharaaj et al. [69] employ transfer learning in their federated learning scheme to achieve personalization in clients as a way to tackle the problem of data heterogeneity across clients. Bowler et al. [45] collected ultrasonic sensor data from laboratory scale fermentations to improve the model prediction accuracy on an industrial scale fermentation process. Their result showed the federated transfer learning methodology achieved higher accuracy for 14 out of 16 machine learning tasks compared to the baseline model.

The distinction between cross-silo and cross-device is difficult to determine at times. The process behind our decision is summarized in Fig. 7. The deciding factor between cross-silo and cross-device is the intended use. If the intention is to create a method for multiple entities, such as data owning organizations, to combine information from their dataset through federated learning, the paper is described as cross-silo. If the intended use is to create a way for combining data from many data capturing devices such as IoT devices or mobile phones, the paper is labelled cross-device. The intended use for cross-device is not always reflected in the experiments which resembled the cross-silo setting. For instance, the work by Khan et al. [93] was aimed at cross-device scenario for UAV devices, however the data used in the experiments originated from a public image dataset and the aspects of cross-device federated learning problems such as large number of devices, problems with connectivity or small computing power are not addressed in the experimental design. Some papers partially address the cross-device challenges in a simulated setting. Park et al. [33] simulate the scheduling of IoT sensors at the edge servers within the federated learning task, bringing it closer to the cross-device scenario. Y. Huang et al. [40] is also classified as cross-device. Although their number of participating clients is low (5), they are heterogeneous and contain mobile phones, reflecting the hardware heterogeneity aspect of this setting. Al-Betar et al. [94] work on a communication-efficient federated learning for edge computing setting that we classify as cross-device. The conducted experiments address the cross-device problem of unstable network communication. The authors themselves also highlight the limitations of their work such as scalability challenges, dependency of network conditions, and real-world implementation challenges such as dropout of devices that are not addressed in the experiments.

Other times, data collected from sensors is classified as cross-silo. While Arshad et al [43] use data from wearable sensor devices, the data is collected centrally within collaborating institutes which resulted in a cross-silo characterization. Gulati et al. [38] do not specify the number of clients, but it is implied that each client is supposed to represent an organization. Vellingiri et al. [34] mentioned sixteen monitoring sites that posed as client nodes, which lead to the assumption

Fig. 6. Distribution of federated learning variants throughout food research. The food research papers using federated learning are categorized using the previously described federated learning framework (Section 2). This figure displays the number of relevant papers with a certain server architecture (left upper corner), type of client node (right upper corner) and data partitioning (left bottom corner).

Fig. 7. Decision flowchart for deciding between cross-silo and cross-device categorization.

that the experimental setting is composed of sixteen data silos. A clear example of cross-silo federated learning is presented by Durrant et al [102], where both the research objective as well as experimental design are aimed at a scenario of organizations with their own datasets collaborating.

4. Discussion: trends, gaps and future outlook

We have reviewed and discussed 86 papers using federated learning in food research. From this, we identified several trends and potential gaps. The research gaps we identified were vertical federated learning for supply chains, federated transfer learning for scarce data scenarios, and decentralized federated learning for scalability. We ordered them in terms of expected impact from highest to lowest.

Very few papers implemented a vertical partitioning of the data. The lack of vertical federated learning is likely due to a specific challenge of vertical federated learning: sharing common identifiers across vertical partitions. This process of entity matching between clients requires additional effort of finding suitable identifiers to track the same sample across organizations. The tracking information is not always readily available. Furthermore, these identifiers may reveal sensitive information about individuals, products, or processes. Safeguarding against attribute linkage attacks requires careful consideration of privacy-preserving techniques and encryption methods [20]. We hypothesize that the problem of entity matching in food research is closely related to the problem of traceability of food across the food supply chain. Traceability of processed foods is challenging due to the variety of raw materials, batch mixing, and resource transformation (J. [127]). The access to the traceability information may also be restricted to food safety competent authorities and not freely available for research purposes. Because of the limited examples of vertically partitioned data in food research, we refer the reader to review papers on vertical federated learning that outline the principles and challenges of vertical federated learning (Y. [20], A. [128]). A notable challenge is stronger reliance on the entire federation for training and inference, emphasizing the need for model fairness and good incentive mechanisms in vertical federated learning. Vertical federated learning also has its own technical challenges such as feature selection in a vertically split federation and entity alignment. As compared to horizontal federated learning, the benefit of using vertical federated learning includes: 1) each party holds different subsets of features, which allows stakeholders to contribute specific domain knowledge and expertise, leading to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the problem; and 2) by focusing on relevant features from different stages of the food supply chain, vertical federated learning can reduce redundancy in data transmission and processing. Such an application could be useful for improving the safety of the food supply chains. The safety of a product is influenced by its production, processing, transportation, storage, and consumption, and the associated data are owned by the company handling each of these steps. The potential of vertical federated learning in supply chains has been recognized by Navidimehr et al. [118], X. Zhang et al. [60], and T.H. Liu et al. [119]. The use of federated learning across different links in food supply chains should be further explored. This way, federated learning could facilitate collaboration between the companies involved in the supply chain, connecting various aspects of food processing and handling into one model for the early warning system of the food supply chain.

We also found a lack of federated transfer learning research. Federated transfer learning provides a head start by initializing the model with knowledge learned from a large, diverse, or available dataset. Fine-tuning with federated transfer learning allows the model to adapt to local data distributions and domain-specific features, which may lead to improved performance and generalization across different food safety scenarios. An example could be the transfer of experimental knowledge to industrial settings. As we saw in the paper by Bowler et al. [45], federated learning can be used as a domain adaptation method allowing

a model to be pretrained on a small-scale experimental setting and adapted to a larger industrial setting. Similar domain adaptation methodology may be applied in other domains that require monitoring. Successful application of transfer learning requires sufficiently related domains. If the domains are not sufficiently related, it can lead to “negative transfer” where the transfer of knowledge from the source domain has a negative impact on the target learner [129].

We found that most papers used centralized server architectures As compared to centralized federated learning, decentralized federated learning improves scalability by distributing computational tasks and communication overhead across multiple client nodes. This enables federated learning to scale to larger networks of participants. Furthermore, decentralized federated learning architectures may be considered in cases where having a single point of failure is a drawback or where the communication with the centralized server is a bottleneck. In food safety, decentralized federated learning could be more suitable for large-scale food safety networks. However, decentralized federated learning also comes with its own challenges. For instance, decentralized federated learning may be more prone to cybersecurity problems [130].

The future employment of IoT technology in food production and monitoring may lead to new data sources suitable for the cross-device federated learning scenario. We already encountered examples of animal behavior sensors [41,42], ultrasonic sensors [45], and remote sensing technology like UAV (F.S. [89,93]) paired with federated learning. Data from IoT devices can be leveraged for tasks optimizing food production such as crop-disease detection, and pest monitoring. IoT sensors, such as temperature and humidity sensors, might also be useful in food safety research [131]. In addition to available data, promising work on synthetic data aided FL has emerged recently [132]. With the increased availability of data, food safety research could leverage large-scale datasets to identify patterns, trends, and correlations that can inform risk assessment, hazard analysis, forecasting food safety risks, and identifying emerging threats and mitigation strategies. However, there is still a lack of experiments conducted in a non-simulated IoT environment. For now, most of the IoT-based agricultural systems are still in the prototypical or conceptual stage [122].

Not all publications in this review were transparent about the way the data was partitioned in terms of the number of clients, the number of samples per client, and the label distributions. In a real-life federated scenario, parts of this information may be obscured. However, federated learning research is often conducted in controlled circumstances with access to the entire dataset that is artificially divided across the clients. Since non-IID data can influence the model performance, it is essential to be transparent about the way the data is divided. We suggest that the inclusion of the data division description in the methods becomes standard practice in future federated learning research, as it puts the results into context and makes the research more reproducible.

Federated learning does not guarantee full protection of the data or the fairness of the models. A plethora of attacks may be used both during and after the training process, and both by an insider or an outsider [133]. For example; malicious agents may use the parameter updates to extract sensitive information about the data (inference attacks) or disrupt (poisoning attacks) the model training [134]. The privacy of the local data can be strengthened with measures such as differential privacy [16] or homomorphic encryption [135], often at the expense of accuracy and efficiency. Such measures were considered in a few of the papers, such as in the work of Durrant et al. [102]. The federated learning process can be made more transparent and robust against malicious agents with blockchain [38]. In the example by Gulati et al. [38], blockchain ensures that only trusted and authorized clients can participate in the federation. Furthermore, federated learning orchestration through a distributed ledger determines which models to aggregate based on desired criteria, in effect preventing aggregation of poisonous model updates and tracking. It also prevents the central server from steering the gradient towards certain (malicious) clients [38]. Official guidelines for best practices in federated learning are needed for

responsible and safe use of local data. The European Union has guidelines for artificial intelligence (AI) models described in the AI Act and best practices on securing machine learning algorithms are provided by European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) [136]. Currently neither source contains concrete and explicit guidelines specifically for federated learning. ENISA also provides guidelines on data-sharing and (pseudo)anonymization. However, to our knowledge, no official policies exist within the European Union that would directly address security and privacy standards of federated learning applications. We recommend that policy makers construct similar guidelines on federated learning, including recommendations on protection against malicious attacks and additional protective measures for privacy such as differential privacy or homomorphic encryption.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) aims to protect personal data of natural persons located within the bounds of the European union (Regulation - 2016/679 - EN - Gdpr - EUR-Lex, n. d.). This applies to the data collected on consumers and employees of food producers. Even with the enhanced privacy protection of federated learning, the model parameters still encode information that could be decoded by a malicious party, disclosing personal information in the process. Therefore, federated learning needs to take the GDPR requirements into account [137]. A federated learning system may process the data on the basis of consent or legitimate interest, because the data is processed with an explicit purpose of training a global model [137]. However, the GDPR requirements of fairness and transparency are a challenge due to the black-box character of many machine learning models and the limited access to the original data and the local models in federated learning specifically [137]. The European Union Trade Secrets Directive [138] has a broader applicability to other types of data for both businesses and non-commercial research institutions. It can form a base for the protection of participating clients in a federated learning system against unlawful breaches of confidentiality.

5. Conclusion

In this review, we collected and summarized 86 papers on federated learning in food research. The output was based on systematic and comprehensive literature search of papers published before August 15th, 2024. We observed that the most used application was crop disease prediction, followed by process monitoring and optimization, and security of food systems. We found two main reasons for federated learning: unwillingness to share the data due to data privacy, ownership and confidentiality, and difficulties with data sharing due to computational limitations. Regarding the federated learning framework, we found that most papers used horizontal and centralized federated learning. There was no clear preference between cross-silo and cross-

11. Appendix

The search was performed on the title, the abstract and the keywords. We obtained the articles using following search terms on July 31, 2023 during the first round of literature collection and August 15, 2024 during the second round of literature collection.

11.1 Search codes for literature search

Web of science

TS= (federated learning OR federated approach)

AND (TS=(food* AND (safety OR monitoring OR supply OR chain OR processing OR market* OR distribution OR storage OR handling OR farm* OR fraud OR hygiene OR surveillance OR agribusiness)) OR TS=(food AND (adulteration OR contaminants OR tempering OR fraud)) OR TS=(water OR food* OR vegetable* OR fruit* OR meat OR fish OR grain OR cereal OR legume* OR milk OR dairy OR egg* OR maize OR rice OR wheat OR flour OR potato* OR onion* OR tomato* OR lettuce OR carrot* OR pepper* OR cucumber* OR celery OR broccoli OR mushroom OR spinach OR cabbage* OR bean* OR cauliflower OR garlic OR asparagus OR banana* OR apple* OR grape* OR strawberries OR melon* OR avocado* OR blueberries OR mandarins OR oranges OR peach* OR pineapple* OR lemon* OR poultry OR chicken* OR pig* OR duck* OR bovine OR beef OR broiler OR salmon OR

device federated learning. We observed that vertical data partitioning, federated transfer learning, and decentralized architectures are less commonly used. We hope that our review will be useful for researchers and companies that aim to use machine learning on food data that previously could not be shared due to privacy concerns.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zuzanna Fendor: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Bas H.M. van der Velden:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Xinxin Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Andrea Jr. Carnoli:** Writing – review & editing. **Osman Mutlu:** Writing – review & editing. **Ali Hürriyetoglu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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tuna OR tilapia OR bacteria OR "Bacillus cereus" OR "Campylobacter jejuni" OR "Clostridium botulinum" OR "Clostridium perfringens" OR "e. coli" OR "Escherichia coli" OR "Listeria monocytogenes" OR Shigella OR "Staphylococcus aureus" OR salmonella OR "Vibrio cholerae" OR "Vibrio parahaemolyticus" OR "Vibrio vulnificus" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "acromobacter sakazakii" OR "Bacteriophage" OR "Enteric Virus" OR "Hepatitis A virus" OR Norovirus OR "Norwalk virus" OR "Rota virus" OR prion OR "Mad Cow Disease" OR "food poisoning" OR fungus OR mycotoxin* OR aflatoxin OR Deoxynivalenol OR "Ochratoxin A" OR Fumonisin OR Patulin OR arsenic OR cadmium OR Mercury OR "heavy metals" OR pesticide* OR pest* OR insecticide* OR fungicide* OR herbicide* OR Azoxystrobin OR Captan OR Clethodim OR Thiocarbamate OR "allergenic" OR "Anaphylactic shock" OR "allergen*") OR TS=(crop* OR agriculture)

NOT TS = ("fine-grained" OR cancer)

Google scholar

("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (food AND (safety OR monitoring OR supply OR chain OR processing OR market* OR distribution OR storage OR handling OR farm* OR fraud OR hygiene OR surveillance OR agribusiness) OR (food AND (adulteration OR contaminants OR tempering OR fraud) OR bacteria OR "Bacillus cereus" OR "Campylobacter jejuni" OR "Clostridium botulinum" OR "Clostridium perfringens" OR "e. coli" OR "Escherichia coli" OR "Listeria monocytogenes" OR Shigella OR "Staphylococcus aureus" OR salmonella OR "Vibrio cholerae" OR "Vibrio parahaemolyticus" OR "Vibrio vulnificus" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "Cronobacter sakazakii" OR "Bacteriophage" OR "Enteric Virus" OR "Hepatitis A" virus OR Norovirus OR "Norwalk virus" OR "Rota virus" OR fungus OR mycotoxin* OR pesticide* OR pest* OR vegetable* OR fruit* OR meat OR fish OR grain OR cereal OR legume* OR milk OR dairy OR egg* OR crop* OR agriculture)

CAB abstracts

CAB abstracts is a database already limited to articles on agriculture and life sciences. Since using just federated learning and federated approach as search terms resulted in only 15 hits, we decided not to narrow it down any more than that.

("federated learning" OR "federated approach")

Scopus (126 hits total):

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (food* AND (safety OR monitoring OR supply OR chain OR processing OR market* OR distribution OR storage OR handling OR farm* OR fraud OR hygiene OR surveillance OR agribusiness)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (food AND (adulteration OR contaminants OR tempering OR fraud)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (water OR food* OR vegetable* OR fruit* OR meat OR fish OR grain OR cereal OR legume* OR milk OR dairy OR egg* OR maize OR rice OR wheat OR flour OR potato* OR onion* OR tomato* OR lettuce OR carrot* OR pepper* OR cucumber* OR celery OR broccoli OR mushroom OR spinach OR cabbage* OR bean* OR cauliflower OR garlic OR asparagus OR banana* OR apple* OR grape* OR strawberries OR melon* OR avocado* OR blueberries OR mandarins OR oranges OR peach* OR pineapple* OR lemon* OR poultry OR chicken* OR pig* OR duck* OR bovine OR beef OR broiler OR salmon OR tuna OR tilapia OR bacteria OR "Bacillus cereus" OR "Campylobacter jejuni" OR "Clostridium botulinum" OR "Clostridium perfringens" OR "e. coli" OR "Escherichia coli" OR "Listeria monocytogenes" OR shigella OR "Staphylococcus aureus" OR salmonella OR "Vibrio cholerae" OR "Vibrio parahaemolyticus" OR "Vibrio vulnificus" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "acromobacter sakazakii" OR "Bacteriophage" OR "Enteric Virus" OR "Hepatitis A virus" OR norovirus OR "Norwalk virus" OR "Rota virus" OR prion OR "Mad Cow Disease" OR "food poisoning" OR fungus OR mycotoxin* OR aflatoxin OR deoxynivalenol OR "Ochratoxin A" OR fumonisin OR patulin OR arsenic OR cadmium OR mercury OR "heavy metals" OR pesticide* OR pest* OR insecticide* OR fungicide* OR herbicide* OR azoxystrobin OR captan OR clethodim OR thiocarbamate OR "allergenic" OR "Anaphylactic shock" OR "allergen*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crop* OR agriculture)) AND NOT TITLE-ABS-KEY ("fine-grained" OR cancer)

IEEE divided into: (83 hits total)

1. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (food* AND (safety OR monitoring OR supply OR chain OR processing OR market* OR distribution OR storage OR handling OR farm* OR fraud OR hygiene OR surveillance OR agribusiness)) **15 hits**
2. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (food AND (adulteration OR contaminants OR tempering OR fraud))
3. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (water OR food* OR vegetable* OR fruit* OR meat OR fish OR grain OR cereal OR legume* OR milk OR dairy OR egg* OR maize OR rice) NOT (FINE-grained OR cancer) **63 hits**
4. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (OR wheat OR flour OR potato* OR onion* OR tomato* OR lettuce OR carrot* OR pepper* OR cucumber* OR celery OR broccoli OR mushroom OR spinach OR cabbage* OR bean* OR cauliflower OR garlic OR asparagus)
5. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (banana* OR apple* OR grape* OR strawberries OR melon* OR avocado* OR blueberries OR mandarins OR oranges OR peach* OR pineapple* OR lemon*)
6. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (poultry OR chicken* OR pig* OR duck* OR bovine OR beef OR broiler OR salmon OR tuna OR tilapia)
7. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (bacteria OR "Bacillus cereus" OR "Campylobacter jejuni" OR "Clostridium botulinum" OR "Clostridium perfringens" OR "e. coli" OR "Escherichia coli" OR "Listeria monocytogenes" OR Shigella OR "Staphylococcus aureus" OR salmonella OR "Vibrio cholerae" OR "Vibrio parahaemolyticus" OR "Vibrio vulnificus")
8. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "acromobacter sakazakii" OR "Bacteriophage" OR "Enteric Virus" OR "Hepatitis A virus" OR Norovirus OR "Norwalk virus" OR "Rota virus" OR prion OR "Mad Cow Disease" OR "food poisoning")
9. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (fungus OR mycotoxin* OR aflatoxin OR Deoxynivalenol OR "Ochratoxin A" OR Fumonisin OR Patulin OR arsenic OR cadmium OR Mercury OR "heavy metals" OR pesticide* OR pest*) **5 hits**
10. ("federated learning" OR "federated approach") AND (insecticide* OR fungicide* OR herbicide* OR Azoxystrobin OR Captan OR Clethodim OR Thiocarbamate OR "allergenic" OR "Anaphylactic shock" OR "allergen*")

11.2 Nomenclature

Abbreviation	
CAB	Commonwealth Agricultural Bureaux
EFRA	Extreme Food Risk Analysis
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IID	Independent and Identically Distributed
IoT	Internet of Things
LVVN	Netherlands Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Food Security and Nature
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

11.3 Detailed categorization of literature within the federated learning framework

This table contains information used for creating Fig. 6. It categorizes each study according to the three distinctions in the federated learning framework in Section 2.

Reference	Architecture	Data Partition	Cross-silo/Cross-device
[75]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[78]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[49]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[94]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[65]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[43]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[66]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[64]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[105]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[51]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[44]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[45]	Centralized	Transfer learning	Cross-silo
[89]	Centralized	Horizontal /Vertical	Cross-device
[95]	Decentralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[32]	Unspecified	Horizontal	Cross-device
[96]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[46]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[82]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[90]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[97]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[102]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[14]	Centralized	Horizontal	Unspecified
[47]	Centralized	Unspecified	Cross-device
[101]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[63]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[59]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[38]	Centralized/Decentralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[109]	Centralized	Transfer learning	Cross-device
[111]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[106]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[84]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[139]	Centralized	Transfer learning	Cross-silo
[30]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[61]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[83]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[36]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[53]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[93]	Centralized	Horizontal	Unspecified
[92]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[67]	Decentralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[107]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[98]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[103]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[41]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[48]	centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[88]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[87]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[99]	Centralized	Horizontal	Unspecified
[76]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[118]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Reference	Architecture	Data Partition	Cross-silo/Cross-device
[108]	Decentralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[54]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[62]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[33]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[50]	Centralized	Unspecified	Cross-device
[110]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[69]	Centralized	Transfer Learning	Cross-device
[104]	Centralized	Vertical	Cross-silo
[79]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[80]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[77]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[56]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[55]	Centralized	Horizontal	Unspecified
[57]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[71]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[126]	Decentralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[58]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[91]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[100]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[86]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[81]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[34]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[37]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[85]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[60]	Centralized/Decentralized	Horizontal/Vertical	Cross-device /Cross-silo
[40]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device
[68]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-silo
[35]	Centralized	Horizontal	Cross-device

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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